

SECUREMED

Enhancement of security and
GDPR compliance for the ICSC
cloud platform

POC SECUREMED

CASCADE CALL - SPOKE 8 – In silico Medicine & Omics Data

THEMATIC AREA :

“Hardening cloud systems for the deployment of in silico medicine solutions on GDPR-compliant platforms”

PROPOSERS:

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OBJECTIVE:

Identify optimal tools and practices aimed at improving security and ensuring compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) within the complex of computing and data management systems.

1

INTEGRATION BETWEEN RUCIO AND KEYCLOAK

A project for secure and modern authentication

Rucio: manage scientific data on a large scale

- **Rucio** is an open source platform **developed at CERN** to manage, organize, and access large-scale distributed scientific data.
- It was developed as part of the **ATLAS** experiment, one of the main experiments at the **Large Hadron Collider (LHC)**, which produces enormous amounts of data to be analyzed around the world.
- Today, Rucio is also used by other LHC experiments and various international scientific communities. Its architecture ensures automatic **replication, traceability, and secure access to distributed datasets**.

Keycloak: the digital identity manager

- Keycloak is an open source platform for **centralized authentication and authorization**.
- Enables **Single Sign-On (SSO)**: one login for multiple services.
- Supports standard protocols such as **OpenID Connect** and **OAuth2**.
- Manages users, roles, and access tokens.
- In this project, Keycloak is Rucio's "**identity guardian**".

Why combine Rucio and Keycloak?

- Replace Rucio's internal authentication with an external system that is more secure and standard.
- Allow login via **OpenID Connect (OIDC)** protocol.
- Centralize user management.
- Simulate a realistic and safe environment, similar to a production setup.
- In summary: Rucio manages data, Keycloak manages identities.

2 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Understanding how components work together to ensure secure authentication and data management

PoC - Rucio-Keycloak integration environment

The environment created is divided into three virtual machines :

- **VM1.** Contains the entire Rucio environment, with storage and the FTS tool for data replication.
- **VM2.** Contains Keycloak for authentication management and identity control
- **VM3.** Contains clients that simulate access and use of the environment

Communication between systems takes place via HTTPS.

Rucio manages data, Keycloak manages authentication.

| How login works: the user journey

- The user accesses Rucio, which requires authentication by Keycloak.
- Keycloak displays the login page and verifies the credentials.
- After login, Keycloak sends Rucio an **identity token**.
- Rucio validates the token and grants access to the data, generating an **access token** in turn.

The token is like a ticket digitally signed by Keycloak and then by Rucio.

Who does what in the system

Rucio

- Coordinates transfers and manages datasets
- Interacts with FTS for automatic file replication
- Tracks the status and location of data in various RSEs

Keycloak

- Authenticate users and services
- Issues OIDC tokens for secure access
- Manage users

FTS (File Transfer Service)

- Physically executes transfers between storage devices
- Receives instructions from Rucio and communicates their status
- Works asynchronously

Who does what in the system

RSE (Rucio Storage Elements)

- They represent data storage points. That is, the physical storage devices on which data is stored.
- In our environment, they are conveniently located on VM1, but they can be located on any other device **accessible on the network**.
- Each RSE has its own protocol, endpoint, and destination space.

End user

- Start upload/download operations via CLI or API
- All operations go through Rucio (authenticated via Keycloak)

The architecture is modular: each service can be located on different hosts, provided they are accessible on the network.

Data replication and distribution

Data replication and distribution is carried out **in close collaboration between Rucio and FTS**.

- Rucio orders the replication of files from one storage (source RSE) to another (destination RSE)
- The operation is performed by FTS, which manages transfer protocols (e.g., GridFTP, HTTPS, xrootd, etc.)
- When finished, Rucio updates the status of the replica in its database

FTS is the engine behind transfers, Rucio is the brain that coordinates them.

From components to flows: Authentication

A user who wants to access or use Rucio is redirected to Keycloak for authentication and, more specifically, for **identity verification**.

Rucio **does not directly manage user login credentials**, but asks Keycloak to take care of it.

Keycloak verifies the identity and, once confirmed, authorizes Rucio to let the user in.

Modular and secure architecture

In summary:

- All services are in Docker containers to ensure **isolation and portability**
- All components communicate via encrypted HTTPS channels
- Keycloak is the system that controls which identities can access the environment (**IP, Identity Provider**)
- Rucio is the system that manages datasets and coordinates replicas (**SP, Service Provider**).
- FTS is the system that **physically** transfers data between one RSE (Rucio Storage Element) and another
- The authentication standard is called **OpenID Connect**.

3 IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS

From plan to action: building the integrated Rucio-Keycloak environment

Construction of the environment

After defining the architecture, the practical implementation phase began

- VM configuration. The necessary software, including Docker, was installed on each VM. The hosts were also **configured for DNS resolution** and an **NTP server was set up** to ensure that all VMs had the same time.
- Installing Rucio and Keycloak via Docker
- Certificate management for **HTTPS protocol** enablement
- Initial connection of the two systems for secure communication

Rucio: entities

Rucio organizes data on three main levels:

- **File:** smallest unit.
- **Dataset:** logical set of files, useful for managing consistent groups of data.
- **Container:** set of datasets or containers, for large-scale groupings.

Each element is a **DID (Data Identifier)** identified by **scope** and **name**. The scope separates the namespaces: two users can have the same name but different scopes.

An authenticated user can only access DIDs within their own scope or shared scopes. Roles and policies define who can create, modify, or read data in each scope.

Keycloak: entities

In Keycloak, among the various configurations to be made, there are :

Realm: It is a logical security container that **isolates** users, roles, and configurations. Each realm manages its own user base, clients, and policies. In our case, the **rucio-demo** realm was created, dedicated exclusively to integration with Rucio.

✦ *Analogy: a realm is like an "independent domain".*

Client: It is an application that uses Keycloak to authenticate users. It defines how Keycloak should interact with it (access type, protocols, redirect URI). Here, the main client is rucio, configured to use the **OpenID Connect** flow with confidential access type.

✦ *Analogy: the client is "the service that trusts Keycloak to identify users".*

User: This is the identity of the end user. Each user belongs to a realm and can have customized roles and attributes. Users can authenticate via password or through external providers (LDAP, SSO).

✦ *Analogy: the user is "the real or technical person who accesses the services".*

Authentication server configuration (Keycloak)

The main operations on Keycloak are:

- Starting the Keycloak container and accessing the Web UI.
- Creation of the **rucio-demo** realm
- Creation of the **rucio** client

The *rucio client* will have the following configurations, among others:

- Access type: confidential
- Standard flow: active
- Redirect URIs: <https://rucio/auth/oidc>,
https://rucio/auth/oidc_code,
https://rucio/auth/oidc_token

The screenshot displays the Keycloak administration interface. On the left, a sidebar menu is visible with the 'rucio-demo' realm selected. The main content area shows the 'Clients' configuration page. At the top, there's a header with the Keycloak logo and the text 'Clients are applications and services that can request authentication of a user. Learn more'. Below this, there are tabs for 'Clients list', 'Initial access token', and 'Client registration'. A search bar is present with the text 'Search for client' and a search icon. To the right of the search bar are buttons for 'Create client', 'Import client', and 'Refresh'. Below these elements is a table listing the configured clients.

Client ID	Name	Type	Description
account	`\${client_account}`	OpenID Connect	–
account-console	`\${client_account-console}`	OpenID Connect	–
admin-cli	`\${client_admin-cli}`	OpenID Connect	–
broker	`\${client_broker}`	OpenID Connect	–
realm-management	`\${client_realm-management}`	OpenID Connect	–
rucio	–	OpenID Connect	–
security-admin-console	`\${client_security-admin-console}`	OpenID Connect	–

Authentication server configuration (Keycloak)

Once you have created **Realm** and **Client**, you can retrieve the **Client Secret**, the key needed to establish a secure connection between **Rucio** and **Keycloak**.

Next, proceed with the **creation of users**, who will access the system through authentication managed by Keycloak.

To ensure correct identity association, **accounts and user IDs** must be **consistent** between Rucio and Keycloak.

The screenshot displays the Keycloak administration interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with a navigation menu including 'Manage', 'Clients', 'Client scopes', 'Realm roles', 'Users', 'Groups', 'Sessions', 'Events', 'Configure', 'Realm settings', 'Authentication', 'Identity providers', and 'User federation'. The main content area shows the 'Clients' page for a client named 'rucio' (OpenID Connect). The 'Credentials' tab is selected, showing a 'Client Authenticator' dropdown set to 'Client Id and Secret' with a 'Save' button below it. The 'Client Secret' field is masked with dots and includes an eye icon to toggle visibility and a 'Regenerate' button. The 'Registration access token' field is also masked and has a 'Regenerate' button. The breadcrumb 'Clients > Client details' is visible at the top of the main area.

Connect Rucio to Keycloak: the idpsecrets.json file

The **idpsecrets.json** file defines the configuration with which Rucio connects to the Keycloak identity provider. It contains all the information necessary to establish secure communication according to the **OpenID Connect (OIDC)** protocol.

Main parameters:

- **issuer:** URL of the Keycloak realm that issues tokens. This is the reference point that identifies the authentication authority.
- **client_id:** Name of the client registered in Keycloak (*here rucio*). This is used to identify Rucio as an application authorized to request tokens.
- **client_secret:** Secret key shared between Rucio and Keycloak. Ensures that only Rucio can authenticate itself as a valid client.

```
{
  "https://keycloak:8443/realms/rucio-demo": {
    "issuer": "https://keycloak:8443/realms/rucio-demo",
    "client_id": "rucio",
    "client_secret": "PNdfxiQjl71b8FlM4vssejeECfGrFGHe",
    "redirect_uris": [
      "https://rucio/auth/oidc",
      "https://rucio/auth/oidc_code",
      "https://rucio/auth/oidc_token"
    ],
    "SCIM": {
      "issuer": "https://keycloak:8443/realms/rucio-demo",
      "client_id": "rucio",
      "client_secret": "PNdfxiQjl71b8FlM4vssejeECfGrFGHe",
      "redirect_uris": [
        "https://rucio/auth/oidc",
        "https://rucio/auth/oidc_code",
        "https://rucio/auth/oidc_token"
      ],
      "token_endpoint_auth_method": "client_secret_basic"
    },
    "token_endpoint_auth_method": "client_secret_basic"
  }
}
```

Connect Rucio to Keycloak: the idpsecrets.json file

- **redirect_uris:** List of Rucio endpoints to which Keycloak can redirect after login. They indicate where Keycloak sends the token once authentication is complete.
- **SCIM:** Optional section with the same information, used by Rucio to manage integration with user provisioning systems or additional APIs.

The **idpsecrets.json** file is the “linking key” between Rucio and Keycloak: it tells Rucio who its Identity Provider is, how to trust it, and where to receive authentication tokens.

```
{
  "https://keycloak:8443/realms/rucio-demo": {
    "issuer": "https://keycloak:8443/realms/rucio-demo",
    "client_id": "rucio",
    "client_secret": "PNdfxiQjl71b8FlM4vssejeECfGrFGHe",
    "redirect_uris": [
      "https://rucio/auth/oidc",
      "https://rucio/auth/oidc_code",
      "https://rucio/auth/oidc_token"
    ],
    "SCIM": {
      "issuer": "https://keycloak:8443/realms/rucio-demo",
      "client_id": "rucio",
      "client_secret": "PNdfxiQjl71b8FlM4vssejeECfGrFGHe",
      "redirect_uris": [
        "https://rucio/auth/oidc",
        "https://rucio/auth/oidc_code",
        "https://rucio/auth/oidc_token"
      ],
      "token_endpoint_auth_method": "client_secret_basic"
    },
    "token_endpoint_auth_method": "client_secret_basic"
  }
}
```

Connect Rucio to Keycloak: the rucio.cfg file

The **rucio.cfg** file contains Rucio's main settings. Specifically, the **[oidc]** section enables authentication via **OpenID Connect (IODC)**, allowing Rucio to communicate with Keycloak.

Parametri principali:

- **idpsecrets:** path to the *idpsecrets.json* file containing the Keycloak connection details.
- **admin_issuer:** URL of the Keycloak realm used for administrative operations, such as service token management.
- **issuer:** Main URL of the identity provider, i.e., the access point to Keycloak for user authentication

```
[oidc]
idpsecrets      = /opt/rucio/etc/idpsecrets.json
admin_issuer    = https://keycloak:8443/realms/rucio-demo
issuer         = https://keycloak:8443/realms/rucio-demo
site_url       = https://rucio
request_timeout = 10
expected_scope  = openid profile email
expected_audience = rucio
```

Connect Rucio to Keycloak: the rucio.cfg file

- **site_url:** URL of the Rucio service, used as a reference for redirects and token validation.
- **expected_scope:** List of attributes required during authentication (e.g., openid, profile, email). Defines what user information should be included in the token.
- **expected_audience:** Name of the client in Keycloak to which the token should be issued (here Rucio). This ensures that the token is issued specifically for the Rucio application.

```
[oidc]
idpsecrets      = /opt/rucio/etc/idpsecrets.json
admin_issuer    = https://keycloak:8443/realms/rucio-demo
issuer          = https://keycloak:8443/realms/rucio-demo
site_url        = https://rucio
request_timeout = 10
expected_scope  = openid profile email
expected_audience = rucio
```

*This section connects Rucio to Keycloak and defines **how** OIDC tokens should be requested, received, and validated, ensuring consistent and secure authentication between the two systems.*

Connect Rucio to Keycloak: Apache

To enable Rucio to communicate securely with Keycloak, the **Apache** configuration file has been updated in a few key places:

- HTTPS activation. SSL module enabled and digital certificates (hostcert.pem, hostkey.pem) configured to ensure encrypted communication between clients, Rucio, and Keycloak.
- Internal proxy management. SSLProxyEngine enabled and ProxyPass configured to Rucio's internal services.
- Authentication endpoints. Aliases enabled for the **/auth** and **/oidc** endpoints, which handle the OpenID Connect authentication flow.

Apache is the secure access point to Rucio.

User creation and connection testing

In order to perform authentication tests between Rucio and Keycloak, you must have **corresponding users on both systems**. Specifically, the user defined in Keycloak must match the one in Rucio.

Alignment between users is essential because **Rucio recognizes the user's identity through OIDC (OpenID Connect)** data provided by Keycloak.

For this reason, the **identity configured in Rucio must "match" the Keycloak user**. In essence, there must be a match between the identity in Rucio and the identity in Keycloak.

After creating and associating identities, it will be possible to:

- Verify communication between Rucio and Keycloak;
- Perform the first token exchange and validate user authentication via Rucio.

User creation and connection testing: Keycloak

As a first step, you need to create the user in **Keycloak**, which will represent the main identity during authentication on Rucio. The user must be **active** and complete with all essential information – *username, email, enabled status, and password*.

These operations can be performed either through the Keycloak **web interface** or through the **CLI** (as shown in the examples below).

The first command creates the user, while the second command **obtains the internal identifier (user_id)** and sets the associated password.

User creation

```
docker exec -it keycloak-keycloak-1 bash -lc '  
/opt/keycloak/bin/kcadm.sh create users -r rucio-demo \  
-s username=root -s enabled=true -s emailVerified=true \  
--truststore /opt/keycloak/truststore.jks --trustpass  
changeit \  
--config /tmp/kc.conf
```

Get USER_ID and set password

```
docker exec -it keycloak-keycloak-1 bash -lc '  
UID=$(/opt/keycloak/bin/kcadm.sh get users -r rucio-demo -q  
username=root \  
--truststore /opt/keycloak/truststore.jks --trustpass changeit \  
--config /tmp/kc.conf | jq -r ".[0].id")  
  
/opt/keycloak/bin/kcadm.sh set-password -r rucio-demo --userid  
"$UID" --new-password "secret" \  
--truststore /opt/keycloak/truststore.jks --trustpass changeit \  
--config /tmp/kc.conf
```

User creation and connection testing: Keycloak

Complete the details for the user created

```
docker exec -it keycloak-keycloak-1 bash -lc '
UID=$(/opt/keycloak/bin/kcadm.sh get users -r rucio-demo -q
username=root \
  --fields id --format csv --noquotes \
  --truststore /opt/keycloak/truststore.jks --trustpass
changeit \
  --config /tmp/kc.conf | tail -n1)

/opt/keycloak/bin/kcadm.sh update users/$UID -r rucio-demo \
  -s "email=root@example.org" -s "emailVerified=true" \
  -s "firstName=Root" -s "lastName=User" -s
"requiredActions=[]" \
  --truststore /opt/keycloak/truststore.jks --trustpass
changeit \
  --config /tmp/kc.conf
```

Overview of the main parameters:

- **rucio-demo:** specifies the realm in Keycloak where the user is created.
- **username:** user name. It must match the one created in Rucio.
- **emailVerified:** in the example, it is set to true for simplicity.
- **update users:** adds the missing data relating to the newly created user.

User creation and connection testing: Rucio

After creating the user in Keycloak, you can proceed with creating the corresponding account in Rucio, associating it with the OIDC identity issued by Keycloak. It is preferable that the account name also matches the one created in Keycloak.

Overview of the main parameters:

- **Account Rucio:** represents the application user in Rucio.
- **Identity OIDC:** is the name Keycloak uses to sign in the user.
- **Issuer:** URL of the Keycloak realm that issues the token.

Account creation

```
rucio-admin account add root --type USER --email root@example.org
```

OIDC identity association with the account

```
rucio-admin identity add \  
  --account root \  
  --type OIDC \  
  --identity root \  
  --issuer https://keycloak:8443/realms/rucio-demo \  
  --email root@example.org  
# Se multi-V0: va aggiunto --vo def
```

4

PRACTICAL USE CASE

From login to data access

Authentication flow

1. Token request

```
rucio --auth-host https://rucio -H https://rucio --auth-  
strategy oidc  
  --oidc-issuer https://keycloak:8443/realms/rucio-demo \  
  --oidc-scope "openid profile email offline_access" \  
  --oidc-audience rucio --account root whoami
```

The terminal provides a URL to paste into the browser in order to authenticate with Keycloak.

2. Authentication link

The user opens the link provided in the previous step in their browser and enters their credentials.

3. Issuance of the OIDC token

After logging in, Keycloak generates an **OIDC token**.

The token can then be pasted onto the Rucio command that is waiting.

4. Saving and outcome

Rucio validates the identity and generates a token that it saves in

```
/tmp/root/.rucio_root/auth_token_for_account_root
```

The token can be used to access Rucio's APIs.

Using the token

Below is an example of calls using the previously obtained token

User list

```
curl -sk https://rucio/accounts \
  -H "X-Rucio-Auth-Token: $TOKEN" \
  -H "X-Rucio-Account: root" \
  -H "X-Rucio-V0: def"
```

Check a user's attributes or roles (ACL)

```
curl -skL https://rucio/accounts/root/attr \
  -H "X-Rucio-Auth-Token: $TOKEN" \
  -H "X-Rucio-Account: root" \
  -H "X-Rucio-V0: def"
```

Identities list associated with each account

```
curl -sk https://rucio/accounts/root/identities \
  -H "X-Rucio-Auth-Token: $TOKEN" \
  -H "X-Rucio-Account: root" \
  -H "X-Rucio-V0: def"
```

List of RSEs

```
curl -sk "https://rucio/rses/?limit=200&offset=0" \
  -H "X-Rucio-Auth-Token: $TOKEN" \
  -H "X-Rucio-Account: root" \
  -H "X-Rucio-V0: def"
```

5 CONTINUOUS SCANNING AND ANALYSIS

| Continuous scanning and analysis

OWASP secureCodeBox (SCB) is an open-source project that provides a Kubernetes-native toolchain for orchestrating automated and continuous security scans.

The goal is to integrate multiple security scanners (SAST/DAST/IAST/network) in a modular way, perform recurring scans, and centralize the results.

Continuous scanning and analysis

Scanners used in OWASP secureCodeBox

- **Trivy:** Analyze container images and software dependencies to identify known vulnerabilities (CVEs) and outdated packages.
- **OWASP ZAP:** Performs dynamic testing on web apps and APIs to detect vulnerabilities such as XSS, SQL injection, and misconfigurations.
- **Semgrep:** Perform static source code analysis (SAST) by identifying insecure patterns based on OWASP rules and best practices.
- **Bandit:** Analyze Python code to identify dangerous constructs, weak credential handling, and common vulnerabilities.
- **Gitleaks:** Scan code repositories to detect accidentally exposed secrets, tokens, or credentials.
- **Nmap:** Performs network scans to identify hosts, open ports, and exposed services.
- **Nuclei:** Apply known vulnerability templates to web targets, automatically identifying CVEs and weak configurations.

6

VULNERABILITY ASSESSMENT

Vulnerabilities found

CRITICAL

Log Injection

Data originating externally (user input, HTTP headers, parameters, query strings, etc.) is recorded in application or infrastructure logs without being properly sanitized or normalized.

Impact

- **Log poisoning / log forgery** – false rumors that confuse analysts and investigations; real events masked or erased by human interpretation.
- **Detection system evasion (SIEM/parser)** – through malformed payloads capable of subverting the behavior of parsers and correlation rules, causing false negatives.
- **XSS sui log viewer** – If the log viewer does not sanitize the logs correctly, it can execute code in the operator's browser (cookie theft, session takeover, execution of administrative actions).
- **Corruption of forensic evidence** – Unreliable logs make it impossible to reconstruct attacks, compromising incident response activities.

Vulnerabilities found

HIGH

Missing Security Headers

Absence of HTTP security headers (e.g., Content-Security-Policy, Strict-Transport-Security, X-Frame-Options, X-Content-Type-Options, Referrer-Policy).

Impact

- **Increased likelihood of XSS** — The absence of CSP makes it easier to execute any injected scripts and therefore steal cookies or take over sessions.
- **Clickjacking made easy** — Without X-Frame-Options or frame-ancestors, a potential attacker can embed WebUI pages in iframes and trick the user into performing sensitive actions.
- **Possible downgrade HTTPS → HTTP** — Without HSTS, clients may be forced into unencrypted connections, exposing traffic and cookies to MITM attacks.
- **Information leak via referrer** — The absence of a Referrer Policy may result in complete URLs (including parameters/tokens) being sent to third parties.

In general, the absence of these headers can facilitate the construction of various types of attacks.

Vulnerabilities found

HIGH

Host Header Injection

The application accepts arbitrary values in the **Host** or **X-Forwarded-Host** headers without validation.

These values are used to construct absolute URLs, links, and redirects within the application. A value controlled by the attacker can therefore alter the links generated or the behavior of the server, enabling open redirects, phishing, and cache poisoning.

Impact

- **Open redirect e phishing** — The attacker can generate “official” links for the app that then redirect to malicious domains, increasing the effectiveness of phishing.
- **Exfiltration of tokens / sensitive data via manipulated URLs** — Manipulated Host values can lead to the creation of URLs containing sensitive tokens or parameters which, if collected or forwarded, allow the exfiltration of information useful to the attacker.
- **Cache poisoning on CDN/proxy** — If the caching system uses the Host header value as part of the cache key, an attacker can cause incorrect or malicious responses to be stored and subsequently distributed to other users.

Vulnerabilities found

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Rate Limiting Bypass

The rate limiter currently relies on unreliable headers (e.g., X-Forwarded-For) provided by the client, which can be forged. During testing, it was possible to send massive requests without being blocked, demonstrating the possibility of bypassing active protections.

Impact

- **Brute force and credential stuffing** — Potential attackers can try credentials or tokens massively without being restricted.
- **DoS** — Possible saturation of CPU, DB, or network resources.
- **Increase in infrastructure costs** — Increased resource consumption and cloud costs.
- **Interruption of critical services** — Endpoints can degrade or crash, impacting legitimate users.

Vulnerabilities found

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Outdated Components

During the scans, the use of components and libraries with obsolete or no longer supported versions was detected.

These versions may contain known vulnerabilities (public CVEs) or no longer receive security updates.

Impact

- **Exposure to known vulnerabilities (CVE)** — A potential attacker can take advantage of public exploits.

Vulnerabilities found

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Information Disclosure

The application displays sensitive information about the environment, including names and versions of services, libraries, and components, in error messages and during normal execution.

Impact

- **Environment fingerprinting** – A potential attacker can obtain precise information about installed components and versions. This information can be used in the development of targeted exploits.

Vulnerabilities found

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Missing Cookie Flags

Session cookies do not have the HttpOnly, Secure, and/or SameSite security flags.

Impact

- **Session theft via XSS** — Without the HttpOnly flag, injected scripts can read session cookies.
- **Cookie transmission over unencrypted connections** — Without the Secure flag, cookies can be sent via HTTP, exposing them to interception.
- **Increased risk of CSRF** — In the absence of the SameSite flag, cookies are also included in cross-site requests, facilitating cross-site request forgery attacks

In general, the absence of these flags can facilitate the construction of different types of attacks.

Vulnerabilities found

MEDIUM

TRACE Method

The HTTP TRACE method is enabled on the application.

This method reflects the request received by the client, including the headers sent (such as cookies or tokens). In production environments, this poses a risk, as it can allow sensitive information to be exfiltrated or exploited in combination with other vulnerabilities (e.g., XSS, session fixation).

Impact

- **Exposure of sensitive headers** — Potential disclosure of cookies, tokens, or authentication data.
- **Greater attack surface** — The TRACE method, if not necessary, increases the potential for abuse.
- **Risks combined with XSS or legacy clients** — In the presence of other vulnerabilities, it can facilitate the exfiltration of information or user sessions.

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